

ROLE OF LINGUOCULTUROLOGY IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of the features of linguoculturology as a scientific discipline. Particular attention is paid to its role in modern linguistics. The development of linguistic and cultural schools in Uzbekistan, Russia and Europe is considered.

Key words: culture, linguistics, linguoculturology, schools of linguoculturology.

Currently, the development of intercultural communication requires continuous study and improvement of mutual understanding among different nations. This is associated with the emergence of new directions in linguistics aimed at studying the peculiarities of various languages and examining the connection between language and various aspects of people's lives. However, in modern society, conflicts related to cultural or linguistic differences persist and, in some cases, arise. The study of linguoculturology is an important aspect for preventing potential conflicts.

Over the past 200 years, scholars have established the integration of linguistics with a range of humanities disciplines, including history, psychology, ethnography, and philosophy. Due to the continuous development of linguistics, complex scientific directions associated with it start to be introduced. Among these scientific directions, scholars highlight linguoculturology, linguopsychology, and others.

This article is dedicated to examining linguoculturology as a comprehensive science that has emerged at the intersection of linguistics and cultural studies. Currently, it focuses on researching various manifestations of the culture of a particular nation, which are reflected and fixed in the language. It is essential to note that this discipline is not merely a combination of possibilities from two related fields but the

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development of new directions in science that enable the consideration and explanation of previously understudied linguistic facts.

At present, there are several definitions for this branch of linguistics. According to the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, it represents a "holistic theoretical-descriptive study of objects as a functioning system of cultural values reflected in language, contrasting the linguoculturological spheres of different languages (peoples) based on the theory of linguistic relativity" [Israfilova, 2010: 219].

Another definition of this science is proposed by V. A. Maslova. The author defines linguoculturology as a "branch of linguistics that emerged at the intersection of linguistics and cultural studies," as a "humanitarian discipline studying the material and spiritual culture embodied in a living national language and manifested in language processes," or as an "integrative field of knowledge that incorporates the results of research in cultural studies and linguistics, ethnolinguistics, and cultural anthropology" [Maslova, 2001: 9-32].

A more detailed explanation of this direction in modern linguistics is provided by V. V. Vorobyov. The scholar understands linguoculturology as a "comprehensive scientific discipline of a synthetic type, studying the interconnection and interaction of culture and language in its functioning and reflecting this process as a holistic structure of units in the unity of their linguistic and non-linguistic (cultural) content using systemic methods and with an orientation towards modern priorities and cultural principles (the system of norms and universal human values)." The main object of linguoculturology, according to the author, is the "interconnection and interaction of culture and language in the process of its functioning and the study of the interpretation of this interaction in a unified systemic integrity," and the subject of this discipline is the "national forms of society's existence, reproduced in the system of language communication and based on its cultural values," everything that constitutes the "linguistic picture of the world." The study of linguoculturological objects is proposed to be conducted using a systemic method, which involves the unity of semantics, semiotics, syntax, and pragmatics, allowing for a "holistic representation of them as units in which linguistic and non-linguistic content are dialectically connected" [Vorobyov, 1997: 32-43].

Thus, linguoculturology is an interdisciplinary and independent scientific discipline. Currently, five main directions of research are distinguished in modern linguoculturology.

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1. Linguoculturology of a specific social group.
2. Linguacultural lexicography.
3. Comparative linguoculturology.
4. Diachronic linguoculturology.
5. Comparative linguoculturology.

Since linguoculturology emerged at the intersection of two sciences, linguistics and cultural studies, it is closely related to ethnolinguistics and sociolinguistics. However, these areas of research are distinct disciplines.

The foundation of modern linguoculturology lies in the study and description of cultural-linguistic features of language, which are determined by the diversity of peoples and their cultures. By the present time, cultural scholars have developed a significant number of approaches to understanding and defining culture.

One of the first works dedicated to the study of linguoculturology is G.B. Palmer's research [Palmer, 1996: 348]. In his study, "Toward a Theory of Cultural Linguistics," the author puts forward ideas about linguoculturology as a new direction in linguistics and emphasizes the need for a serious study of the peculiarities of the interaction between the culture of a people and the language used by that people. Palmer underscored the necessary and obvious connection between culture and language. His ideas were supported by the researcher F. Sharifian in later works. In his studies on the Persian language, the researcher repeatedly referred to Palmer's research [Sharifian, 2011, 2015].

Researcher Sabrieva believes that culture influences all aspects of language activity, both in the pronunciation of the same phrases in different cultural contexts and in the grammatical features of the same language used in connection with a specific culturological aspect. Moreover, as the scholar asserts, the connection between language and culture is as evident as the interpenetration of different cultures when interacting with each other. Thus, the author concludes that linguoculturology is one of the most important aspects in the study of intercultural communication. This is because knowledge of the culturological and linguistic aspects of a particular language undoubtedly helps establish contact between people from different societies [Sabrieva, 2014: 178-182].

Similar ideas are held by J.B. Paul and A. Cole, who consider linguoculturology, examining the peculiarities of the political aspect of this discipline. The authors write that in politics, understanding both the culture and language of the population of one's

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own country, as well as understanding one's political opponent, is crucial. The researchers hypothesize that the unwillingness to reconcile with linguistic and culturological realities was one of the reasons for events in European countries such as Spain (issues with the Catalonia republic) and the United Kingdom (Brexit issues). Scholars note that one of the problems in the conflict was the linguistic and cultural aspect [Harguindéguy, 2017: 34-37].

According to the researcher Liu Zhuanya, linguoculturology in Russia is represented by several developed schools, each of which has its own principles, scope, and specific analysis procedures. The Moscow Linguoculturological School is represented by N.A. Arutyunova, V.V. Vorobyov, V.V. Krasnykh, V.A. Maslova, Yu.S. Stepanov, and V.N. Teliya [Liu Z. 2013: 857-859]. Yu.S. Stepanov is the author of the work "Constants. Dictionary of Russian Culture," where he examines the constants of Russian folk culture in a diachronic aspect. As the author notes, "in the Russian language, there are concepts - values of Russian culture and, in general, Russian culture that belong to everyone and no one individually. To use them, they need to be known at least through a dictionary compiled by someone." In the work "Linguoculturology as a New Direction in Foreign Language Teaching" by N.E. Sharipova, linguoculturology is considered as a comprehensive direction studying national languages and the manifested cultural peculiarities in language processes, both material and spiritual [Sharipova, 2015: 993-995]. V.N. Teliya focused on the linguoculturological analysis of phraseologisms. The main goal of V.N. Teliya's research and her students is to examine, study, and describe the cultural and ethnic connotative semantics of phraseologisms, as well as identify personal characteristics of consciousness [Teliya, 1996: 288].

V.V. Vorobyov expands the concept of E.M. Vereshchagin and V.G. Kostomarov [Vereshchagin, Kostomarov 1980]. According to his ideas, linguoculturology is oriented towards a new system of cultural values, which is shaped by the peculiarities of modern society's life and objective information about cultural life in the country. V.V. Vorobyov proposed the main unit of linguoculturological analysis - "lingvoculturema," defining it as a "dialectical unity of linguistic and extra-linguistic (conceptual and substantive) content." And the lingvoculturema has a connotative meaning and "lives as long as the ideological context that spawned it" [Vorobyov, 1997: 52].

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Liu Z. emphasizes that in Russia, there are also other schools dealing with serious study of the peculiarities of linguoculturology [Liu, 2013: 857-859]. In addition to the mentioned author, the book "Linguacultural Situation in Contemporary Russia" by Miheeva L.N., Dolinina I.V., Zdorikova Yu.N. is dedicated to the study of this scientific direction. In this research, scientists note the peculiarities of the linguoculturological situation in Russia at the present time. As examples, they analyze youth discourse, which allows identifying the features of the linguistic personality of a young Russian [Miheeva L.N., Dolinina I.V., Zdorikova Yu.N., 2014: 250].

Currently, significant attention is given to the problems of linguoculturology. The need to study this scientific discipline is recognized not only in Russia but also in European countries. New schools are emerging in Russia and abroad, engaged in the study of linguoculturological features of various languages. Scientific research is being conducted not only on widely used languages but also on their regional variations and less-known languages. From the above, it can be concluded that linguoculturology is of interest to modern researchers.

Therefore, linguoculturology is an important branch of linguistics that requires a serious study of the interaction between the culture and language of each country and each nation. However, due to the existence of a large number of languages in the world, as well as the presence of different cultures, subcultures, and micro cultures in society, there is currently a wide variety of approaches to studying this aspect. Moreover, since linguoculturology is a relatively young scientific discipline, the quantity and quality of approaches to its study will continue to grow. Thus, predicting the possible development and influence of this science on the future of linguistics is practically impossible. However, it cannot be denied that this aspect will continue to interest scholars for a long time.

Examining the peculiarities of linguoculturology, we believe that linguoculturology is one of the quite complex and comprehensive aspects of linguistics, as there is a significant number of different cultures and languages at present. However, this scientific direction is in continuous development, driven by constant changes in language and culture. Linguoculturology plays an important role in linguistics as an interdisciplinary field, and the data obtained from research will allow practical application of this information. Studying the linguoculturological features of various countries will impact mutual understanding among populations and intercultural

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communication. However, linguoculturology remains a young and understudied field of science, providing researchers with diverse material for scientific work.

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